

Conclusion. The intricate interplay between AIT and infertility presents a significant clinical challenge for women seeking pregnancy. While the precise mechanisms remain under investigation, our review highlights diverse pathways, including direct hormonal effects, inflammatory dysregulation, and potential shared genetic predispositions. The potential impact on various aspects of fertility, from ovulation disturbances to increased miscarriage risk and suboptimal ART outcomes, underscores the importance of early diagnosis, meticulous thyroid function management, and individualized treatment strategies.

JAK INHIBITORS: MODERN ASPECTS OF AR DRUGS

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Introduction. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) remains a significant burden globally, necessitating the constant evolution of therapeutic strategies. Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors have emerged as promising agents in the management of RA due to their ability to target key inflammatory pathways. Despite their efficacy, there remains a need to comprehensively evaluate their modern aspects to optimize their clinical utility.

The aim of the study. This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of JAK inhibitors as modern antirheumatic (AR) drugs, encompassing their mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics, clinical efficacy, safety profile, and emerging trends in their usage.

Materials and methods. A systematic review of 2000-2024 studies in major medical databases including PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane Library, with relevant keywords such as «JAK inhibitors», «rheumatoid arthritis», «clinical trials», and «safety». Data regarding mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics, clinical efficacy, safety profile, and recent advancements/emerging trends in the field were extracted and synthesized.

Results. Mechanism of action: JAK inhibitors selectively block JAK proteins, crucial for transmitting inflammatory cytokine signals, like IL-6

and TNF- α . This disrupts key RA pathways, reducing inflammation and potentially slowing joint damage. **Pharmacokinetics:** Orally administered with good bioavailability, but dosing varies depending on the specific inhibitor (e.g., tofacitinib 5mg BD, baricitinib 4mg OD, upadacitinib 15mg OD). **Clinical efficacy:** Clinical trials show significant improvements in disease activity scores (DAS28), reduced joint damage progression measured by X-rays, and enhanced physical function/patient-reported outcomes compared to some conventional DMARDs. **Safety Profile:** Favorable profile, but potential risks like upper and lower respiratory tract infections, UTIs, cytopenias, thrombosis, malignancy, adiposity, pain and hyperlipidemia require monitoring. Ongoing research investigates specific safety concerns, including cardiovascular risks. **Emerging Trends:** New formulations exploring sustained release or targeted delivery aim to improve efficacy and reduce side effects. Research on combination therapy with other AR drugs shows promise in complex cases.

Conclusion. JAK inhibitors, with their unique mechanism, proven efficacy, and acceptable safety profile, represent a valuable addition to the AR drug armamentarium. Continued research will refine their role in RA treatment and potentially expand their application to other inflammatory conditions, paving the way for personalized and optimized therapy strategies.

NTM-PULMONARY DISEASE CASE CAUSED BY M.KANSASII ACOMPLICATED WITH PULMONARY ASPERGILLOSIS

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Background. Clinical management of non-tuberculous pulmonary disease (NTM-PD) is challenging in many low- and middle-income countries where limited resources focus primarily on the management of tuberculosis, leaving NTM infections somewhat